

Abstract

A review of the use of video games for the assessment of anxiety

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Abstract: This study presents an analysis of [1], particularly the utilization of videogames and their impact on anxiety levels. By investigating the potential of videogames as assessment tools for anxiety, this review aimed to determine their viability in measuring and addressing anxiety-related concerns. The screening process led to the final selection of 10 articles that met the eligibility criteria. Among these studies, an equal number focused on using videogames and virtual reality (VR) to address anxiety. Notably, the findings revealed a strong emphasis on VR for assessing anxiety disorders, while videogames were predominantly utilized in studies targeting general anxiety levels. Furthermore, three of the selected studies incorporated machine learning techniques to enhance assessment accuracy. Although only two of the chosen studies were clinical in nature, the majority of the findings indicated promising results, supporting the use of videogames as valuable tools for assessing anxiety. This served as a parting point to propose a videogame for the assessment of anxiety symptoms using artificial intelligence, particularly case-based reasoning.

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